

INVESTIGATION OF THE PROTECTIVE CAPABILITIES OF GLASS FROM LASER SOUNDING DEPENDING ON ITS ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION

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Abstract

One of the most vulnerable issues in the technical protection of information is to obtain data via leakage through the opto-electronic channel.

In this paper, studies of the protective capabilities of glass from laser sounding depending on its elemental composition were carried out using such indicators as the coefficients of reflection and absorption of the laser beam by the window glass.

As a result of the work, an experimental installation based on a continuous solid-state laser was assembled.

The study of the elemental composition of window glass, which is produced by modern industry, X-ray fluorescence method and the study of the coefficients of reflection and absorption of glass samples in the experimental setup showed that the studied window glass chemically belongs to quartz (silicate).

All chemical elements involved in its formation can be divided into 3 groups: glass-forming, transitional, modifiers, which affects the optical properties of the studied glasses, as the elements used have different not only qualitative but also quantitative parameters.

Absorption increases if the number of chemical elements that exhibit amphoteric and non-metallic properties and have (-charge) decreases, and increases if the number of chemical elements in the glass that exhibit the most alkaline, alkaline earth properties and in which the radius of cations (+ions) increases.

Systematization of the elemental and quantitative composition of the studied window glass in accordance with the periods and groups of the periodic table of chemical elements, enabled the relationship between the electronic structure of chemical elements and the protective properties of glass.

Keywords: information protection, laser acoustic reconnaissance systems, absorption coefficient, reflection coefficient.

DOI: 10.21303/2461-4262.2022.002527

1. Introduction

There has been a major breakthrough in information security recently, especially in the protection of telecommunications systems and software environments. Many publications deal with protecting information from hacker attacks, malware, attacks on banking systems, and the development of new cryptographic algorithms, etc. [1–3].

However, this all applies to the so-called computer unit of cybersecurity. But in terms of technical protection of information, recently a small percentage of scientific developments have been implemented. One of the most vulnerable issues concerning the technical protection of

information is the obtaining of data both private and confidential due to leakage through the opto-electronic channel [4]. As it is well-known, the main source of these data is laser acoustic reconnaissance systems.

In 2020, this vulnerability was further developed. The technique, which experts have called Lamphone [5], is based on the fact that objects vibrate when compressed with a sound wave. Vibrations create small flashes in a steady stream of light. According to the researchers, if one uses powerful enough sensors, these changes in illumination can be detected and then reconstruct the sound waves that affected the surface of the bulb.

Military operations became an important problem in countering laser intelligence systems. During military operations, optical systems laser detectors operate in the infrared range and catch the reflection of the probing beam from the lens of an optical sight or other optical device [6].

In works [7, 8], domestic scientists consider the issue of speech information protection from leakage by using an opto-electronic channel.

A passive method using sun-protective window films is proposed. As a result, authors concluded that sun protective coatings do not provide the desired effect as anti-laser. Article [9] describes films based on copper compounds that protect windows from radiation in the ultraviolet and visible infrared ranges. These films work most efficiently in the 500 nm range, which cannot provide the desired protection against scanning, because lasers work in the wave range of 650–3000 nm. Authors of the paper [10] analyzed options for reducing glass vibration and preventing laser eavesdropping. Paper considers the design influence of the double-glazed window on the protective properties from laser scanning. The results of the analysis show that only 1 % of the glass vibration is transmitted by the window frames, and everything else is transmitted through window glass.

To combat these vulnerabilities, many different areas have been developed, such as protection of speech information using active methods: special devices (noise generators, vibrators, acoustic protection, magnetostatics (implemented by metal application of tracks or darts placed in parallel on different windows), electrostatics (due to the deposition of a layer of metal on the entire window surface. When the voltage is applied to the sprayed layer, there is an electric field [11–13].

Protection of speech information from laser reading using the so-called passive methods (creation of special window constructions, blinds and curtains for windows). One of the most relevant and promising areas of passive protection of speech information today is the development of various coatings and, accordingly, specialized films. Studies in this direction have begun almost recently, as a rule, many films with narrowly focused characteristics have been created (shockproof, anti-glare, blackout, etc.).

Shockproof films include Kingshield and 3M films, which work on the principle of impact-resistant glass and are applied to the outside of the glass [14, 15].

Anti-glare films include Guardian, 3M, which work on the principle of reflector and absorber of solar and ultraviolet radiation. These films, in contrast to shockproof, are applied to the inside of the glass [16, 17].

Gila, SmartTint, 3M are bright representatives of darkening films. Such films mainly act as dimmers of sunlight and light, however, as well as anti-reflective, they have the effect of absorbing radiation, although not so significant [18–20].

The developed «Signals Defenses» films, in addition to shock-resistant and anti-explosion properties, also have the effect of attenuating radio frequency waves and infrared radiation. The use of such films on glass provides privacy, data protection and acoustic information. «Signals Defenses» films are used by the US government to attenuate radio frequency signals and optical radiation of the infrared spectrum with both high transmittance in the visible light range and low reflection coefficient. This reduces the impact of devices operating in these ranges, in particular laser microphones [21].

A review of literary sources on this issue makes it possible to assert, that one of the most relevant and promising areas of passive protection from laser reconnaissance systems to date is the development of various coatings and, accordingly, specialized films. Nowadays, anti-laser coatings are in the process of development.

In addition, in the conditions of military operations, laser scanning systems are increasingly used for aiming high-precision weapons to destroy military equipment, UAVs, etc. Accordingly,

research on the protective properties of glass from laser probing depending on its elemental composition and development of anti-laser coatings is a relevant issue in the field of information protection in the conditions of military operations and hybrid warfare.

Therefore, the aim of our work is the research of protective properties of the most common industrial glass from laser probing depending on its elemental composition using such indicators as the reflection and absorption coefficients of the laser beam by window glass and detection of dependence between elemental composition and protective properties of glass.

To achieve the aim, the following objectives are set:

- investigate the elemental composition of window glass and the reflection and absorption coefficients;

- consider the dependence of optical properties on the elemental composition of window glass;

- determine the possibilities of predicting the protective properties of glass from the modeling of the components of its elemental composition.

To date, anti-laser coatings are under development.

Therefore, the aim of our research is to study the protective properties of glass from laser sounding depending on its elemental composition using such indicators as the coefficients of reflection and absorption of the laser beam by the window glass.

In accordance with the aim, preliminary experimental studies of the influence of the elemental composition of glass on improving the protection of speech information from laser reading are conducted [22–25].

2. Materials and methods

The most common glass in Ukraine was used for research.

The window sheet glass polished of the M1, M4 brands is produced by float technology (CJSC Lysychansk glass factory Proletaryi). Light transmission coefficient – 0.89, reflection – 0.08, direct transmission of solar energy – 0.83, absorption of solar energy – 0.11, heat transfer coefficient – 5.8 W/m² [26].

Float glass is of the Saint-Gobain Glass company of the SGG Diamant brand (France). Coefficient of light transmission – 0.91, reflection – 0.08, direct transmission of solar energy – 0.88, absorption of solar energy – 0.02 [27].

Float glass is of magnetron coating of the Guardian company of the ExtraClear brand (USA). The light transmission coefficient is 0.81, the reflection is 0.12, the direct transmission of solar energy is 0.89, and the absorption of solar energy is 0.16 [28].

Euroglas Eurofloat is of uncoated glass from Euroglas (Germany). Light transmission coefficient – 0.89–0.91, reflection – 0.08, direct transmission of solar energy – 0.83–0.87, absorption of solar energy – 0.05–0.10 [29].

Pilkington Optifloat is a float glass company for the production of sheet glass NSG Group, operating under the brand Pilkington (UK). Light transmission coefficient – 0.75, reflection – 0.07, direct transmission of solar energy – 0.71, absorption of solar energy – 0.44–0.10 [30].

Orionglass – the newest, sheet, safe (tempered) glass of the Euroglas company (Ukraine). Light transmission coefficient – 0.89, reflection – 0.08, direct transmission of solar energy – 0.11, absorption of solar energy – >25 %, heat transfer coefficient – 5.8 W/m² [31].

Elemental analysis of glass, the most common in the Ukrainian market, was performed on an X-ray fluorescence analyzer of elemental composition «EXPERT 3L» [32].

The X-ray fluorescence method consists in the fact that the sample is exposed to primary X-ray radiation, under the influence of which there is a secondary radiation of the sample, the nature of which depends on the qualitative and quantitative composition of the analyte. Universal calibration, which is stored for the entire period of operation of the device allows not only to operate the analyzer without the use of standard samples, but also without pre-adjustment and calibration to perform multi-element qualitative and quantitative analysis of samples of any (including unknown) composition and arbitrary shape.

The «EXPERT 3L» model provides quantitative definition of elements in any types of alloys (both standard, and non-standard). Analyzer «EXPERT 3L» can also be used for qualitative

and evaluative quantitative elemental analysis of various types of non-metallic samples (polymeric and lubricant materials, building materials, ores, minerals and other objects of natural and artificial origin, etc.). In the presence of the corresponding standards of chemical composition of the specified objects, their precise quantitative analysis can be conducted.

The measurement result is a table of chemical elements detected in the sample and their corresponding mass concentrations with an error of determination of 0.01 % by mass. The «EXPERT» analyzer makes it possible to analyze samples of the substance from magnesium (12) to uranium (92).

To measure the intensity of the reflected laser beam and the one that passed through the sample of the laser beam [33], the installation was assembled according to the optical scheme in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1. Optical scheme of installation: *L* – laser; *S* – sample; *D*₁, *D*₂ – detector (device for measuring the power of laser radiation)

To measure the power of the laser beam, a laser power meter Pocket Laser Power Meter [34] 840011 with a wavelength measurement range of 400–1100 nanometers, measurement accuracy $\pm 5\%$ was applied.

A continuous-action semiconductor laser (660 nm, 150 mW) was used (**Fig. 3**). The visible area was selected to visualize the laser beam.

The laser, the test sample and the *D*₂ detector were on the same optical axis. Detector *D*₁ was placed perpendicular to the optical axis. The position of the detector *D*₁ is used to measure the power of the laser radiation reflected from the surface of the sample, and the position *D*₂ is used to measure the power of the beam passed through the sample. During the measurement, the installation was in a darkened room. The ML101U29 laser diode [35] is a high-power, high-efficiency semiconductor laser based on the AlGaInP semiconductor. Optical radiation power is of 150 milliWatts. The diode provides continuous generation of one transverse mode with a radiation wavelength of 660 nm. The study error was 5 %, which meets the requirements for the wavelength emitted by this laser.

The reflection coefficients (K_{refl}) and absorption (K_{absorp}) of the laser beam were chosen as the protection parameters.

Using the above installation the following was measured:

- the power of the reflected beam from the test sample P_{refl} ;
- absorbed power of laser radiation of the sample P_{absorp} .

The reflection coefficient was found by (1):

$$K_{refl} = \frac{P_{refl}}{P_{absorp}}, \quad (1)$$

where P_{imp} – solid-state laser power.

The power of the laser radiation absorbed by the sample was evaluated according to (2):

$$K_{absorp} = \frac{P_{absorp}}{P_{imp}}. \quad (2)$$

3. Results and discussion

The data obtained by the EXPERT 3L analyzer are presented in the form of diagrams in Fig. 2–7. For the convenience of tables and dependencies, there are all types of glass the following abbreviation:

- 1) SAINT-GOBAIN, 6 mm thick – S-6;
- 2) SAINT-GOBAIN, 4 mm thick – S-4;
- 3) SAINT-GOBAIN, 3 mm thick – S-3;
- 4) ORION-GLASS, 4 mm thick – O-4;
- 5) ORION-GLASS, 6 mm thick – O-6;
- 6) Lysychansk, 6 mm thick – L-6;
- 7) Lysychansk, 4 mm thick – L-4;
- 8) Guardian, 6 mm thick – G-6;
- 9) Euroglas, 4 mm thick – Eu-4;
- 10) Pinkilgton, 4 mm thick – P-4.

In Fig. 2–7 diagrams of qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the studied window glass, which are summarized in the Table 1 are provided.

Fig. 2. Diagrams of qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the studied Lysychanck-4 window glass

Fig. 3. Diagrams of qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the studied window glass: a – Lysychansk-6; b – Saint-Goban-4

The calculated protection parameters (1), (2) were taken by a laser scanning device and presented in Fig. 8, 9.

Fig. 4. Diagrams of qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the studied window glass:
a – Saint-Gobain-6; b – Saint-Gobain-3

Fig. 5. Diagrams of qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the studied window glass:
a – Orion Glass-4; b – Orion Glass-6

Fig. 6. Diagrams of qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the studied window glass:
a – Guardian-6; b – Euro Glass-4

Fig. 8, 9 show that the absorption and reflection coefficients are changed according to the type of glass.

Therefore, based on the elemental and quantitative composition of the existing studied window glass (**Tables 1–3**) and security parameters (**Fig. 3–7**), let's present in **Tables 4–7** protective

characteristics (reflection-absorption) in accordance with the qualitative and quantitative characteristics according to the periodic table.

Fig. 7. Diagrams of qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the studied *Pinkligton-4* window glass

Fig. 8. Coefficients of reflection of the studied window glass

Fig. 9. Absorption coefficients of the studied window glass

Table 1Elemental (Si, Ca, Fe, Na, S, Ti, Sr, Zr, Sn) and quantitative composition (%) of the studied window glass
(where Reflection is green and Absorption is yellow) (n/d-not detected)

Glass/ Elements	Si	Ca	Fe	Na	S	Ti	Sr	Zr	Sn
S-6 0.299	55.2	41.4	0.476	2.251	0.372	0.101	0.066	0.027	0.024
L-6 0.257	54.7	39	0.466	2.724	0.466	0.103	0.045	0.036	0.023
S-4 0.233	54.9	41.2	0.502	1.831	0.482	0.129	0.066	0.022	0.028
P-4 0.224	56.7	37	0.586	2.149	0.466	0.094	0.046	0.027	0.023
O-6 0.218	67.3	29.5	0.785	2.037	n/d	0.248	0.03	0.041	0.047
O-4 0.204	78.3	21	0.185	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.021	0.054	0.024
G-6 0.2	57.3	37	0.482	2.378	0.321	0.085	0.057	0.019	0.022
S-3 0.195	54.2	41.2	0.551	3.117	0.614	0.076	0.038	0.02	0.043
Eu-4 0.18	55	38.4	0.569	2.408	0.589	0.071	0.044	0.028	0.044
L-4 0.171	55.3	40.1	0.502	1.73	0.547	0.144	0.036	0.023	0.056
S-3 1.152	54.2	41.2	0.482	3.117	0.614	0.076	0.038	0.02	0.043
S-4 1.117	54.9	41.2	0.502	1.831	0.482	0.129	0.066	0.022	0.028
S-6 1.117	55.2	41.4	0.476	2.251	0.372	0.101	0.066	0.027	0.024
L-4 1.099	55.3	40.1	0.502	1.73	0.547	0.144	0.036	0.023	0.056
G-6 0.977	57.3	37	0.482	2.378	0.321	0.085	0.057	0.019	0.022
Eu-4 0.681	55	38.4	0.568	2.408	0.589	0.071	0.044	0.028	0.044
O-4 0.663	78.3	21	0.185	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.021	0.054	0.024
L-6 0.628	54.7	39	0.466	2.724	0.466	0.103	0.045	0.036	0.023
O-6 0.611	67.3	29.5	0.785	2.037	n/d	0.248	0.03	0.041	0.047
P-4 0.454	56.7	37	0.586	2.149	0.466	0.094	0.046	0.027	0.023

Table 2Elemental (Mg, Ni, Rb, Y, Nb, Ag, Sb, I, As) and quantitative composition (%) of the studied window glass
(where Reflection is green and Absorption is yellow) (n/d-not detected)

Glass/Elements	Mg	Ni	Rb	Y	Nb	Ag	Sb	I	As
S-6 0.299	n/d	0.003							
L-6 0.257	2.407	n/d	0.005	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.044	0.002
S-4 0.233	n/d	0.004	n/d	0.004	0.004	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
P-4 0.224	2.695	n/d	0.004	0.004	0.004	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
O-6 0.218	n/d	n/d	0.021	0.008	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
O-4 0.204	n/d	0.03	n/d						
G-6 0.2	2.093	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.007	0.023	0.039	n/d
S-3 0.195	n/d	0.005	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.024	0.027	n/d
Eu-4 0.18	2.661	0.004	0.004	n/d	0.004	n/d	n/d	0.036	0.002
L-4 0.171	2.004	n/d	0.004	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.019	0.003
S-3 1.152	n/d	0.005	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.023	0.027	n/d
S-4 1.117	n/d	0.004	n/d	0.004	0.004	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
S-6 1.117	n/d	0.003							
L-4 1.099	2.004	n/d	0.004	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.019	0.003
G-6 0.977	2.093	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.007	0.023	0.039	n/d
Eu-4 0.681	2.661	0.004	0.004	n/d	0.004	n/d	n/d	0.036	0.002
O-4 0.663	n/d	0.03	n/d						
L-6 0.628	2.407	n/d	0.005	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.044	0.002
O-6 0.611	n/d	n/d	0.021	0.008	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
P-4 0.454	2.695	n/d	0.004	0.004	0.004	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d

Table 3

Elemental (Mn, K, Pb, Br, Cd, Ge, Ba, La, Mo, Zn) and quantitative composition (%) of the studied window glass (where Reflection is green and Absorption is yellow), (n/d-not detected)

Glass/Elements	Mn	K	Pb	Br	Cd	Ge	Ba	La	Mo	Zn
S-6 0.299	n/d	n/d	0.004	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
L-6 0.257	0.01	n/d	0.01	n/d						
S-4 0.233	n/d	n/d	0.009	n/d	0.015	0.002	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.003
P-4 0.224	n/d	n/d	0.007	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.004
O-6 0.218	n/d	2.031	0.018	0.003	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.006
O-4 0.204	n/d	n/d	0.008	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.068	n/d	n/d
G-6 0.2	n/d	n/d	n/d							
S-3 0.195	0.029	n/d	n/d	0.002						
Eu-4 0.18	0.012	n/d	n/d	n/d						
L-4 0.171	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.145	0.217	n/d	n/d
S-3 1.152	0.029	n/d	n/d	0.002						
S-4 1.117	n/d	n/d	0.009	n/d	0.015	0.002	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.004
S-6 1.117	n/d	n/d	0.004	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d
L-4 1.099	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.145	0.217	n/d	n/d
G-6 0.977	n/d	n/d	n/d							
Eu-4 0.681	0.012	n/d	n/d	n/d						
O-4 0.663	n/d	n/d	0.008	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.068	n/d	n/d
L-6 0.628	0.01	n/d	0.01	n/d						
O-6 0.611	n/d	2.031	0.004	0.003	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.006
P-4 0.454	n/d	n/d	0.007	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	n/d	0.004

Having studied the elemental and quantitative composition of the studied window glass, let's distributed the chemical elements according to the periods and groups of the periodic table of chemical elements.

Table 4

The relationship of the reflection coefficient with the elemental composition of the studied glass in accordance with the periodic table of chemical elements (by periods) (n/d-not detected)

Glass	Reflection coef- ficient	Elemental composition			
		3 rd period	4 th period	5 th period	6 th period
S-6	0.0299	[Na Si S]	[Ca Ti Zn Fe As]	[Sr Zr Sn]	n/d
L-6	0.0257	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Mn Fe As]	[Rb Sr Zr Mo Sn I]	n/d
S-4	0.0233	[Na Si S]	[Ca Ti Fe Ge Ni Zn]	[Sr Y Zr Nb Cd Sn]	[Pb]
P-4	0.0224	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Fe Zn]	[Rb Sr Y Zr Nb Sn]	[Pb]
O-6	0.0218	[Si]	[K Ca Ti Fe Zn]	[Rb Sr Y Zr Sn]	[Pb]
O-4	0.0204	[Si]	[Ca Ti Fe]	[Sr Zr Sn I]	[La Pb]
G-6	0.0200	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Fe Ni]	[Rb Sr Y Zr Nb Ag Sn Sb I]	n/d
S-3	0.0195	[Na Si S]	[Ca Ti Mn Fe Ni Zn Br]	[Sr Zn Mo Sn Sb I]	n/d
Eu-4	0.0180	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Mn Fe Ni As]	[Rb Rh Sr Zr Nb Sn I]	n/d
L-4	0.0171	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Mn Fe As]	[Rb Sr Zr Sn I]	[Ba La]

Table 5

The relationship of the reflection coefficient with the elemental composition of the studied glass in accordance with the periodic table of chemical elements (by groups)

Glass	Reflection coefficient	Elemental composition							
		1 st group	2 nd group	3 rd group	4 th group	5 th group	6 th group	7 th group	8 th group
S-6	0.0299	[Na]	[Ca Zn Sr]	n/d	[Si Sn] [Ti Zr]	[As]	[S]	n/d	[Fe]
L-6	0.0257	[Na Rb]	[Mg Ca Sr]	n/d	[Si Sn] [Ti Zr]	[As]	[S] [Mo]	[Mn] [I]	[Fe]
S-4	0.0233	[Na]	[Ca Sr] [Zn Cd]	[Y]	[Si Ge Sn Pb] [Ti Zr]	[Nb]	[S]	n/d	[Fe Ni]
P-4	0.0224	[Na Rb]	[Mg Ca Sr] [Zn]	[Y]	[Si Sn Pb] [Ti Zr]	[Nb]	[S]	n/d	[Fe]
O-6	0.0218	[K Rb]	[Ca Sr] [Zn]	[Y]	[Si Sn Pb] [Ti Zr]	n/d	n/d	n/d	[Fe]
O-4	0.0204	n/d	[Ca Sr]	[La]	[Si Sn Pb] [Ti Zr]	n/d	n/d	[I]	[Fe]
G-6	0.0200	[Na Rb] [Ag]	[Mg Ca Sr]	[Y]	[Si Sn] [Ti]	[Nb] [Sb]	[S]	[I]	[Fe Ni]
S-3	0.0195	[Na]	[Ca Sr] [Zn]	n/d	[Si Sn] [Ti]	[Sb]	[S] [Mo]	[Br] [Mn] [I]	[Fe Ni]
Eu-4	0.0180	[Na Rb]	[Mg Ca Sr]	n/d	[Si Sn] [Ti Zr]	[As][Nb]	[S]	[Mn] [I]	[Fe Ni] [Rh]
L-4	0.0171	[Na Rb]	[Mg Ca Sr Ba]	[La]	[Si Sn] [Ti Zr]	[As]	[S]	[I] [Mn]	[Fe]

From **Tables 4, 5** it is seen that the reflection coefficient changes according to the change in the chemical composition of the studied glass. This is due to the presence in the composition of the studied glass of such chemical elements as: Rb, Ag, Zn, Cd, Ba, La, Pb, Mn, I and others, the radii and electronic structure of which cause, in our opinion, a significant impact on the protective properties of the studied glass from laser acoustic reconnaissance systems, namely a decrease in the reflection coefficient and an increase in the absorption coefficient. This makes it possible to predict the properties and model the chemical composition of glass with the specified protective properties.

Table 6

The relationship of the absorption coefficient with the elemental composition of the studied glass in accordance with the periodic table of chemical elements

Glass	Absorption coefficient	Elemental composition			
		3 rd period	4 th period	5 th period	6 th period
G-6	0.151	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Fe Ni]	[Rb Sr Y Zr Nb Ag Sn Sb I]	n/d
L-4	0.114	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Mn Fe As]	[Rb Sr Zr Sn I]	[Ba La]
Eu-4	0.112	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Mn Fe Ni As]	[Rb Rh Sr Zr Nb Sn I]	n/d
P-4	0.095	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Fe Zn]	[Rb Sr Y Zr Nb Sn]	[Pb]
S-3	0.092	[Na Si S]	[Ca Ti Mn Fe Ni Zn Br]	[Sr Zn Mo Sn Sb I]	n/d
O-4	0.089	[Si]	[Ca Ti Fe]	[Sr Zr Sn I]	[La Pb]
O-6	0.082	[Si]	[K Ca Ti Fe Zn]	[Rb Sr Y Zr Sn]	[Pb]
L-6	0.075	[Na Mg Si S]	[Ca Ti Mn Fe As]	[Rb Sr Zr Mo Sn I]	n/d
S-6	0.051	[Na Si S]	[Ca Ti Zn Fe As]	[Sr Zr Sn]	n/d
S-4	0.042	[Na Si S]	[Ca Ti Fe Ge Ni Zn]	[Sr Y Zr Nb Cd Sn]	[Pb]

Tables 6, 7 confirm the general pattern of the relationship between the reflection and absorption coefficients. Chemical elements that promote reflection reduce the absorption coefficient. The mechanism of this dependence, in our opinion, is explained by the electronic structure of atoms of chemical elements (filling of s-, p-, d-, f-levels of elements and their corresponding radii).

Table 7

The relationship of the absorption coefficient with the elemental composition of the studied glass in accordance with the periodic table of chemical elements (by groups)

Glass	Absorption coefficient	Elemental composition							
		1 st group	2 nd group	3 rd group	4 th group	5 th group	6 th group	7 th group	8 th group
G-6	0.151	[Na Rb] [Ag]	[Mg Ca Sr]	[Y]	[Si Sn] [Ti]	[Nb] [Sb]	[S]	[I]	[Fe Ni]
L-4	0.114	[Na Rb]	[Mg Ca Sr Ba]	[La]	[Si Sn] [Ti Zr]	[As]	[S]	[I] [Mn]	[Fe]
Eu-4	0.112	[Na Rb]	[Mg Ca Sr]	n/d	[Si Sn] [Ti Zr]	[As] [Nb]	[S]	[Mn] [I]	[Fe Ni] [Rh]
P-4	0.095	[Na Rb]	[Mg Ca Sr] [Zn]	[Y]	[Si Sn Pb] [Ti Zr]	[Nb]	[S]	n/d	[Fe]
S-3	0.092	[Na]	[Ca Sr] [Zn]	n/d	[Si Sn] [Ti]	[Sb]	[S] [Mo]	[Br] [Mn] [I]	[Fe Ni]
O-4	0.089	n/d	[Ca Sr]	[La]	[Si Sn Pb] [Ti Zr]	n/d	n/d	[I]	[Fe]
O-6	0.082	[K Rb]	[Ca Sr] [Zn]	[Y]	[Si Sn Pb] [Ti Zr]	n/d	n/d	n/d	[Fe]
L-6	0.075	[Na Rb]	[Mg Ca Sr]	n/d	[Si Sn] [Ti Zr]	[As]	[S] [Mo]	[Mn] [I]	[Fe]
S-6	0.051	[Na]	[Ca Zn Sr]	n/d	[Si Sn] [Ti Zr]	[As]	[S]	n/d	[Fe]
S-4	0.042	[Na]	[Ca Sr] [Zn Cd]	[Y]	[Si Ge Sn Pb] [Ti Zr]	[Nb]	[S]	n/d	[Fe Ni]

As a result of the research, an experimental setup based on a solid-state continuous laser with a wavelength of 660 nm and a Pocket Laser Power Meter 840011 was assembled.

The study of the elemental composition of window glass, which is produced by modern industry, X-ray fluorescence method and the study of reflection and absorption coefficients of glass samples in the experimental setup showed that the studied window glass by chemical composition are quartz (silicate), and all chemical elements involved in the construction of these glasses are located in the periodic table of chemical elements in the 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th periods and within the Ist, IInd, IIIrd, IVth, Vth, VIth groups.

Accordingly, if to consider the composition of window glass, all the chemical elements involved in its formation can be divided into 3 groups: glass-forming (Na, Ca, Si, Ge, As), transitional (compounds based on Fe, Ti, Mn, Ag, Co, Cu, Sb), modifiers (oxides of alkali and alkaline earth metals), which affects the optical properties of the studied glasses, as the elements used have different not only qualitative but also quantitative parameters.

Absorption increases if the number of chemical elements that exhibit amphoteric and non-metallic properties and have (-charge) decreases, and increases if the number of chemical elements that exhibit the most alkaline, alkaline earth properties and in which the radius of cations (+ions) increases.

Lead (Pb), as an impurity related to heavy metals, leads to an increase in the reflection coefficient, probably due to a change in density. Rare earth elements, such as Ba, La – despite the ionic radii, reduce reflection.

During our research, certain limitations were encountered that may slightly affect the obtained results. These restrictions include:

- a small number of types of window glass in Ukraine;
- the maximum effect of anti-laser properties of window glass can be achieved only by conducting research on spectrophotometers at different wavelengths;
- different resolutions and errors of spectrophotometers that can be used for research;
- slight discrepancy in the results of the same glass produced in different batches;
- the need for a vacuum environment to maintain the purity of the glass.

The socio-economic effect of the implementation of the proposed results can be expected in the form of a reduction in public spending at the expense of:

- reduction of information leakage through vibroacoustic and optical information leakage channels;
- reducing the costs on vibroacoustic systems for protecting window glass from laser acoustic reconnaissance systems;

- increasing the level of stealth of special forces from enemy detection by laser detection systems;
- saving the lives of special forces personnel.

4. Conclusions

A qualitative and quantitative analysis of window glass was carried out and the chemical elements identified in its composition were distributed according to the periods and groups of the periodic table of chemical elements. The correlation of reflection and absorption coefficients with the elemental composition of the studied glass was established according to the periodic table of chemical elements (by periods and groups).

It was established that the reflection and absorption coefficients change according to the change in the chemical composition of the examined glass. This is due to the presence of such chemical elements in the composition of the investigated glass: Rb, Ag, Zn, Cd, Ba, La, Pb, Mn, I and other, the radii and electronic structure of which have a significant effect on the protective properties of the investigated glass from laser acoustic reconnaissance systems, namely, a decrease in the reflection coefficient and an increase in the absorption coefficient. The mechanism of this dependence, in our opinion, is explained by the electronic structure of atoms of chemical elements (fullness of s-, p-, d-, f-levels of elements and their corresponding radii).

Systematization of the elemental and quantitative composition of the studied window glass according to the periods and groups of the periodic table of chemical elements, made it possible to see the dependence between the electronic structure of chemical elements and the protective properties of glass. Such studies make it possible to model the component composition and predict the protective properties of glass.

As follows, systematization of the elemental and quantitative composition of the studied window glass in accordance with the periods and groups of the periodic table of chemical elements, enabled the relationship between the electronic structure of chemical elements and the protective properties of glass. Such studies allow to model the composition and predict the protective properties of glass.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Received date 13.07.2021

Accepted date 28.07.2022

Published date 30.09.2022

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How to cite: Dzianyi, N., Dudykevych, V., Opriskyy, I., Rakobovchuk, L., Haraniuk, P. (2022). Investigation of the protective capabilities of glass from laser sounding depending on its elemental composition. *EUREKA: Physics and Engineering*, 5, 162–174. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21303/2461-4262.2022.002527>